

ASPECTS OF FORMATION OF POSITIVE QUALITIES IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Kudyarova Artikgul

*Student of the Faculty of primary education of
The Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz*

Abstract. This article discusses the methods, conditions, specifics, psychological conditions, etc., for the formation of positive qualities in primary school students.

Keywords: Positive quality, primary school, child, formation, opportunity.

INTRODUCTION

With admission to school, the child expands the opportunities for the formation of many personal properties. First of all, it should be said about the complex of special personality traits that relate to the motivation to achieve success.

As is well known, the prerequisites for the formation of this motive are already beginning to take shape at preschool age. However, the final formation and consolidation of the motivation for achieving success (avoiding failure) as a personality trait occurs in the early school years. What properties are included in the complex associated with the implementation of this motivation?

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

First of all, it is necessary to note the even more intensified, in comparison with preschoolers, boundless trust in adults, mainly teachers, submission and

imitation of them. This is expressed so much that, characterizing himself, the younger student necessarily repeats what adults say about him.

The assessment of adults directly affects the self-esteem of children. And in younger schoolchildren, unlike preschoolers, self-esteem is differentiated and can be adequate, overestimated, underestimated. This must be taken into account by adults and be careful in their conclusions regarding the abilities, qualities, successes, failures of children of primary school age.

RESULTS

Secondly, it is necessary to note such a feature as the conscious setting of goals for achieving success and volitional regulation of behavior, which allows the child to achieve it. This suggests that the child has already formed the subordination of goals to the motives of activity. So, children, interested in something, can be carried away by this activity for hours.

The motivation for achieving success (avoiding failure) is directly related to self-esteem (as mentioned above) and the level of aspirations of the individual. This connection is traced as follows. Experimental studies have shown that individuals with a strong motivation to achieve success and a low motivation to avoid failures have an adequate moderately high self-esteem, as well as a fairly high level of aspirations. Therefore, in the process of developing the motive for achieving success in children, it is necessary to take care of both self-esteem and the level of claims.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The school is the main link in the system of education of the younger generation. At each stage of the child's education, its own side of education dominates. In the education of younger schoolchildren, Yu.K. Babansky, moral

education will be such a side: children master simple moral norms, learn to follow them in various situations. The educational process is closely connected with moral education. In the conditions of the modern school, when the content of education has increased in volume and become more complex in its internal structure, the role of extracurricular reading in moral education is increasing. The content side of moral concepts is due to the scientific knowledge that students receive by studying literature. Moral knowledge itself is no less important for the overall development of schoolchildren than knowledge in specific academic subjects.

N.I. Boldyrev notes that a specific feature of moral education is that it cannot be separated into some special educational process. The formation of moral character takes place in the process of all the multifaceted activities of children (playing, studying), in those various relationships that they enter into in various situations with their peers, with children younger than themselves and with adults. Nevertheless, moral education is a purposeful process that involves a certain system of content, forms, methods and techniques of pedagogical actions.

Considering the system of moral education, N.E. Kovalev, B.F. Raysky, N.A. Sorokin distinguish several aspects:

Firstly, the implementation of the coordinated educational influences of the teacher and the student team in solving certain pedagogical problems, and within the class - the unity of action of all students.

Secondly, the use of methods for the formation of educational activities by moral education.

Thirdly, the system of moral education is also understood as the interconnection and mutual influence of the moral qualities being brought up at the moment in children.

Fourthly, the system of moral education should also be seen in the sequence of development of certain personality traits as children grow and mentally mature.

In the formation of the personality of a junior schoolchild, from the point of view of S.L. Rubinshtein, a special place is occupied by the development of moral qualities that form the basis of behavior.

At this age, the child not only learns the essence of moral categories, but also learns to evaluate their knowledge in the actions and actions of others, their own actions.

CONCLUSIONS

An essential feature of the process of moral education is its concentric construction: the solution of educational problems begins with the elementary level and ends with a higher one. To achieve the goals, all the more complex types of activities are used. This principle is implemented taking into account the age characteristics of students.

The process of moral education is dynamic and creative: teachers constantly make their own adjustments to it, aimed at its improvement.

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